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ABSTRACTS

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Synthesis of ceramic nanocomposites for dental restoration

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Abstract. This research aims in a new approach to enhance dental cement's mechanical stability through synthesizing nanocomposites using a non-hydrolytic sol-gel process. The composition includes polymer ceramic nanocomposites. The synthesis procedure entails combining methyl methacrylate powder with ceramic nanoparticles and zinc oxide, followed by polymerization with a cross-linker liquid. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) characterization revealed distinctive bonds in zirconium and silicate compounds, while X-ray Diffraction (XRD) discerned their structural characteristics. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) scrutinized particle distribution in dental cement, and particle size and radiopacity analyses provided insights into their behavior under X-ray. Biological assessments included a hemolysis assay to evaluate the impact on red blood cells (RBCs) and an MTT assay to assess cytotoxicity in cellular interactions. The findings offer valuable insights into the potential of these nanocomposites to enhance the mechanical properties of dental cement, thereby advancing the field of dental biomaterials. This research holds implications for the broader domain of biomaterial science and its applications in dentistry, contributing to the ongoing progress in dental material research.

Keywords: Polymer, nanocomposites, dental restoration

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